

Impact of Tobacco and Recreational Cannabis Smoking on Male Reproductive Health: A Comparative Look at Sperm Parameters, Chromatin Integrity and Oxidative Damage

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ABSTRACT

Male infertility, accounting for approximately 50% of infertile couples' cases ^[1], and is gradually leading to depression and other psychological outcomes, and this might be potential signs of serious future consequences.

The negative impact of tobacco smoking on a wide range of physiological functions is well-established. Moreover, the consumption of tobacco and cannabis poses a growing risk to male reproductive health. Numerous studies over recent decades have indicated a correlation between smoking tobacco or cannabis and a decline in sperm quality, potentially leading to male infertility. This study aims to explore and discern the effects of tobacco and cannabis use on sperm quality, chromatin integrity, and oxidative damage among men under 40 years old.

A total of 116 semen samples were collected from men who undergoing semen analysis at assisted reproduction laboratory. The samples were divided into three groups: Group 1 - Non-smokers (control group, n=38), Group 2 - Tobacco smokers (n=39), and Group 3 - Cannabis smokers (n=37). Chromatin integrity and DNA damage was assessed by using Chromomycine CMA₃ and Acridine Orange staining. The 8-OHG RNA assay was employed to measure oxidative damage.

Sperm count and progressive motility showed no significant difference between the investigated groups (non-smokers, tobacco smokers, and cannabis smokers).

However, the mean value of immotile spermatozoa and morphologically abnormal spermatozoa increased among smokers and cannabis smokers compared to non-smokers (52.42% for smokers, 65.13% for cannabis smokers and 44.59% for non-smokers).

(5.02 for smokers, 2.23 for cannabis smokers and 7.34 for non-smokers) respectively.

In addition, the mean value of chromatin condensation of spermatozoa showed a statistically significant difference among non-smokers (14.68 ± 15.64), tobacco smokers (25.28 ± 14.86 ; $P \leq .024$), and cannabis smokers (34.83 ± 18.39 ; $P \leq .001$).

This study demonstrates that tobacco and cannabis smoking have a negative effect on sperm parameters, chromatin condensation (Sperm maturity) and DNA integrity of spermatozoa and should be avoided in men undergoing assisted reproduction treatment.

Keywords: Smoking; Cannabis Smoking; Male infertility; Sperm cells

INTRODUCTION

Tobacco use remains prevalent worldwide. According to the World Health Organization, 22.3% of the global population, 36.7% of men and 7.8% of women, used tobacco in 2020^[2].

Cigarette smoking is a recognized health hazard, and the highest prevalence of smokers is in young men of reproductive age^[3]. It was estimated that 5.5% of the global population aged 15–64 have used cannabis recreationally^[4]. According to world drug Report 2019: 35 million people worldwide suffer from drug use disorders while only 1 in 7 people receive treatment.

Over the past few decades, there has been a growing concern about the impact of tobacco and cannabis smoking on male reproductive health. Therefore, understanding their potential effects on fertility is crucial for the well-being of future generations.

The correlation between tobacco smoke and both cardiovascular- and cancer-related morbidity has been well-established; additionally, recent research has underscored the detrimental effects of tobacco smoke on male fertility^[5,6].

Tobacco is comprised of numerous toxic and mutagenic compounds, among which nicotine, potent psychoactive substance, and its primary metabolite cotinine can traverse the blood-testis barrier, subsequently inflicting varying degrees of damage upon germ cells^[7].

Furthermore, existing studies have substantiated the notion that tobacco smoke can act as both a mutagen and an an-eugen within germ cells/spermatozoa^[8,9].

There is a pile of evidence suggest that tobacco smoking has a negative impact on male fertility. While there may be some debate surrounding its effects on sperm motility, it is widely recognized that it can lead to reductions in sperm concentration, morphologically normal spermatozoa, and altered protein expression in addition to genetic and epigenetic anomalies within spermatozoa^[10].

Also, Smoking is closely linked to abnormalities in histone-to-protamine transition and with alteration of protamine expression in human spermatozoa. Patients who smoke possess a higher proportion of spermatozoa with an alteration of the histone to protamine ratio than patients who do not smoke^[11].

Various studies have provided insights into the multiple pathways through which tobacco smoking affects sperm cells. One salient mechanism is the direct toxicological impact of the constituents of cigarette smoke on testicular function^[12]. For instance, it has been discovered that nicotine impairs spermatogenesis by inducing oxidative stress, DNA damage, and apoptosis within germ cells, leading to reduced sperm count and motility^[13].

These outcomes can be attributed to the augmented generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which subsequently provokes oxidative stress (OS), DNA impairment, and germ cell apoptosis. Additionally, tobacco smoking is known to increase seminal reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels, which disrupt sperm functionality and results in decreased fertilization capacity^[14].

While ROS is essential for certain physiological processes^[15], excessive accumulation can lead to DNA strand fractures, unsaturated lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial function disruption, and oxidative DNA damage^[16,17]. Spermatozoa are particularly susceptible to ROS due to the presence of limited cytoplasmic antioxidants and restricted repair mechanisms^[18]. Owing to the translational and transcriptional inert nature of DNA, damage sustained in sperm DNA remains persistent.

However, it is also important to consider that a multitude of risk factors have been postulated in relation to male infertility, encompassing erectile dysfunction, varicocele, congenital dysplasia, endocrinological disorders, immunological aspects, sexually transmitted infections, and exposure to chemicals as well as radiation^[19].

It is worth mentioning that, approximately 9% of daily tobacco smokers also smoke cannabis daily^[20]. and 40%–54% of cannabis users reported smoking cigarettes in the past 30 days^[21]. Many studies have documented various reproductive anomalies, including compromised spermatogenesis, diminished semen quality, and modified sperm functionality in men who consume tobacco and cannabis^[22,23].

There classification of cannabis from a class B to a class C drug in 2004, along with its potential application in multiple sclerosis treatment and utilizing synthetic THC (Dronabinol) in the United States and certain European countries for alleviating cachexia associated with AIDS, reducing nausea stemming from cancer chemotherapy, and addressing chronic pain as well as anxiety, has led to widespread misconceptions regarding its legality and health implications^[24]. In 2021, 44% of adults surveyed believed smoking marijuana every day is safer than smoking tobacco every day, compared to about 37% in 2017^[25]. Marijuana is the most widely used recreational drug, containing THC, which can negatively impact normal reproductive functions^[26].

The utilization of cannabis has been scientifically demonstrated to induce substantial morphological alterations in spermatozoa, manifesting as aberrant morphologies in experimental models with rodents such as mice and rats [27]. Notwithstanding these findings, it is essential to note that prevailing research suggests that there is no association between cannabis use and chromosomal fragmentation within spermatozoa, implying to the preservation of genetic material [28].

In a separate investigation conducted on male individuals aged 30 and under who consumed cannabis within a 90-day period before providing a semen sample exhibited a higher likelihood of abnormal sperm morphology [29].

In the study from Gundersen et al. regular use of marijuana was found to be associated with an impairment in semen quality, while irregular use seems to be irrelevant [30]. Previous study conducted by Kolodny et al reported that 20 heterosexual men who had used marijuana at least four days a week for a minimum of six months experienced reduced plasma testosterone, oligospermia, and impotence [31].

Also, RNA and DNA are perhaps the most critical biological targets affected by oxidative damage. Recent studies have linked oxidative harm in RNA molecules to a spectrum of neurological disorders, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, Down syndrome, dementia with Lewy bodies, prion disease, sub-acute sclerosing pan-encephalitis, and xeroderma pigmentosum. Among numerous types of RNA oxidative damage, the formation of 8-hydroxyguanosine (8-OHG) is a ubiquitous marker of oxidative stress [32].

Additionally, [33] observed an escalation in seminal ROS levels, accompanied by an increased sperm DNA fragmentation index and elevated 8-hydroxy-2-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) concentration in semen samples gathered from smoking males.

Understanding the potential consequences of cigarette and cannabis smoking and their impact on male is crucial especially for men in reproductive age.

Therefore, this study is conducted to determine and compare the impact of tobacco and cannabis smoking on sperm parameters, chromatin integrity, and oxidative damage as key indicators of male reproductive health.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total of 116 samples were collected from men aged less than 40 years at Prince Rashid bin Al Hassan Hospital (PRBH) in Irbid, Jordan and from IVF British-Syrian IVF center, Damascus, Syria.

Our participants' ages range between 25 to 40 years old, with all individuals hailing from West Asian backgrounds. We structured our participants into three distinct groups for this study:

1. Group 1 'NN' consists of non-smokers_ non-Cannabis who serve as the control group, with a total number of 38 individuals. Control group participants have no history of tobacco or cannabis use.
2. Group 2 'SN' includes tobacco smokers but non-cannabis, with a participant count of 39. These individuals have been smoking more than 10 cigarettes daily for at least five years. Participants in tobacco smoker group have exclusively used tobacco and have never used cannabis or any other recreational drug.

3. Group 3 'SC' encompasses cannabis smokers, made up of 37 participants. Each participant within this group has been using cannabis for more than three years, consuming at least four joints per week. Most participants within our cannabis smoker group are also current tobacco users or at least have smoked tobacco in the past.

Patients with varicocele, alcoholic problems, and genetic abnormalities such as Klinefelter's syndrome were excluded from the study.

To procure participants, we utilized a direct recruitment approach at the clinic level. Our target demographic was healthy, fertile men who were potential candidates for providing sperm samples pertinent to our research. To initiate participation, we developed a comprehensive questionnaire designed to ascertain whether individuals would meet the rigorous criteria established for our study.

Participants were then carefully selected based upon their responses, placing particular emphasis on lifestyle habits such as smoking; individuals were grouped accordingly based on their smoking habits. This allowed us to examine any variations attributed to such behaviors within the dataset.

Semen samples were collected from all subjects by masturbation after 3 to 5 days of sexual restraint. Thereafter, semen analysis was done within 30 minutes to 1 hour of ejaculation also following a period of incubation at 37°C to allow for liquefaction according to WHO recommendations (WHO, 2021).

Following measurement of semen volume, samples were analyzed using standard light microscopy within one hour of ejaculation. Several 10 µL smears of each sample were done to evaluate spermatozoa morphology, chromatin integrity using chromomycin (CMA₃), DNA strand breaks by acridine orange assays (AO).

Each donor was: a) in good physical and mental health, b) free from any hereditary diseases, c) tested negative for HIV types 1 and 2, syphilis, hepatitis B and C, herpes, and cytomegalovirus, d) showing no bacterial infections in blood or semen cultures, and e) possessing a seminal profile that surpasses the minimum standards set by the World Health Organization guidelines. Semen analysis, sperm chromatin condensation integrity with Chromomycin (CMA₃) staining, sperm viability, DNA fragmentation (Acridine Orange) and DNA-RNA oxidative damage were compared between the study groups.

Chromomycin CMA₃

Chromatin integrity in human sperm was evaluated by Chromomycin (CMA₃) staining method. Briefly, the air-dried semen smears were fixed in methanol-glacial acetic acid 3:1 at 4°C for 60 minutes and then allowed to air dry at room temperature. 50 µL of CMA₃ stain solution (0.25 mg CMA₃/mL in McIlvain's buffer PH 7.0, supplemented with 10 mmol/L Mg Cl₂) was added to each slide and covered with coverslips then incubated in the dark for 30 minutes at room temperature.

Lastly, each slide was rinsed with PBS buffer and mounted with 1:1 (v/v) PBS/glycerol then kept at 4°C overnight. A total of 200 spermatozoa were observed on each slide under fluorescent microscope with a 460-nm filter and 10 eyepiece magnifications. The evaluation of chromatin condensation state was performed by

distinguishing spermatozoa with bright yellow stain (CMA₃ positive) from those with a dull yellow stain (CMA₃ negative).

Acridine Orange (AO)

The analysis of DNA fragmentation in spermatozoa was evaluated by using Acridine Orange fluorescence staining. This staining was performed according to the methods described thoroughly by ^[34]. Briefly, 1. air-dried semen smears were fixed for 2 hours in freshly prepared Carnoy's solution (Methanol/glacial acetic acid 3:1), then air dried

2. Smears were stained with acid Acridine Orange solution

3. All smears were prepared for assessment using fluorescence microscope. For this study, each slide was carefully examined to analyze 200 sperm cells. Acridine Orange (AO), a fluorescent dye, was used to differentiate the DNA integrity within these cells. AO intercalates with double-stranded DNA; however, in sperm cells with immature nuclei, DNA are readily denatured into single strands. This results in an aggregation of AO molecules within the nuclei, emitting an orange-red fluorescence. Conversely, sperm nuclei with intact double-stranded DNA exhibit green fluorescence. This distinction allows for the identification of spermatozoa with denatured (orange or yellow, AO positive) and normal (green, AO negative) DNA ^[35].

Observations were carried out using a BX51 fluorescence microscope from Olympus Corporation equipped with a 480–490 nm filter. The percentages of spermatozoa displaying green fluorescence, indicating normal DNA integrity, and orange-red fluorescence, which signals abnormal DNA integrity were then calculated.

ROS measurements

The Oxidative DNA-RNA oxidative damage evaluated by applying Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) kit.

The Oxidative RNA Damage Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) kit is competitive immunoassay for the accurate quantification of 8-hydroxyguanosine (8-OHG) (Cell Biolabs company).

Initially, the 8-OHG samples of unknown concentrations or established 8-OHG standards are incorporated into a pre-absorbed EIA plate featuring an 8-OHG/BSA conjugate. Following a brief incubation period, a highly specific anti-8-OHG monoclonal antibody is introduced, succeeded by the addition of a horseradish peroxidase (HRP)-conjugated secondary antibody. The precise 8-OHG content in the unknown samples was ascertained through comparison to a predetermined 8-OHG reference curve (36).

Statistical Analyses:

The Kruskal-Wallis H test was employed to discern statistically significant differences in sperm parameters, AO, CMA3, and 8-OHG RNA damage content among the three groups. Non-smokers, smokers, and cannabis smokers.

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS 17.0 (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Data with normal distribution are presented as mean \pm standard deviation, and a P-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The Shapiro-Wilk test determined the normality of data distribution. For comparison among multiple groups with equal variances, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed. Conversely, for non-normally distributed variables, the Mann-Whitney U test was applied as appropriate.

Ethical approval was obtained by local ethical committees.

A written consent was obtained from each participant in this study. In addition, this study was approved by the Jordanian Royal Medical Services-Human Research Ethics Committee, with the project identification code (TF3/1/Ethics Committee/9126).

RESULTS

Routine semen parameters in the cigarette (Tables 1) and cannabis smoking groups (Tables 2) were compared with those of the non-smoking group.

Sperm counts was (59.64 \pm 23.9) mill /mL for non-smokers, 57.92 \pm 21.6 mill /mL for smokers and 46.71 \pm 18.1 mill /mL for cannabis smokers ($p = 0.159$). Progressive motility was 57.02 \pm 11.15 % for non-smokers, 60.77 \pm 10.5 % for smokers, and 46.21 % for cannabis smokers, $p = 0.110$).

Although the sperm count and progressive motility exhibited minor reductions, also, neither the counts nor the motility showed statistically significant differences between the three investigated groups (Table 1 and 2). In both groups, cigarette smoking or cannabis smoking, no significant differences in sperm concentration or sperm motility were found between the smoking and non-smoking groups.

On the contrary, the findings revealed a statistically significant discrepancy in the immotile sperm count across distinct smoking categories. A notable variation was observed in the quantity of immotile sperms and sperms exhibiting abnormal morphology among the groups studied.

The immotile spermatozoa demonstrated a statistically significant increase in smokers and cannabis smokers in comparison to non-smokers (44.59 \pm 18.5 mill/mL) for non-smokers; 52.42 \pm 24.30 mill/mL for smokers, and 65.13 \pm 21.8 mill/mL) for cannabis smokers $p \leq 0.020$).

There was virtually no statistically significant difference between non-smoker and tobacco smoker groups. However, a significant difference in immotile sperm was observed exclusively between the non-smoker and cannabis smoker group. The difference between tobacco smoker group and cannabis smoker groups less pronounced (Table 2).

Concurrently, the mean number of morphologically normal spermatozoa exhibited a significant decline as a follow (7.34± 5.8 % for non-smokers, 5.2.02±4.8% for smokers, and 2.232±2.1% for cannabis smokers’ p ≤ 0.001).

Also, no discernible differences were found between tobacco smokers and non-smokers groups (P ≤ 0 .152). However, a statistically significant difference (P ≤ 0.001) was identified between the cannabis smoker group and both non-smoker and tobacco smoker groups.

The mean percentage of Chromatin condensation CMA3 was (14.68±15.64 % for non-smokers 25.28±14.86%for tobacco smokers and 34.83±18.39%cannabis smokers).

The percentage of abnormal sperm chromatin condensation was significantly higher in smokers compared to nonsmokers (p ≤ 0.001).

A statistically significant difference in mean values was observed between the investigated groups (p ≤0.001).A post hoc analysis using the Turkey HSD- test indicated that non-smokers exhibited considerably lower CMA3+ scores compared to both tobacco and cannabis smokers.

The mean percentage of spermatozoa stained positively with Acridine Orange (DNA damage) was (10.08±14.2 % for non-smokers, 16.5±10.2 % for tobacco smokers, and 28.5± 15.8% for cannabis smokers. However, no significant difference deference was observed in the mean percentage of AO positive stained samples (DNA damage) among the groups (p≤0.481)

Furthermore, the mean concentrations of DNA-RNA Oxidative Damage were 40.74±18.2 for non-smokers, 46.26±19.30 for tobacco smokers, and 88.42± 22.40 for cannabis smokers (Tables 1, 2, 3).

The proportion of oxidative damage in the cannabis smoker cohort was significantly elevated in comparison to both non-smoker and tobacco smoker groups (p ≤ 0.001). (Table 2,3).

Upon utilizing the one-way ANOVA technique to analyze data collected from the groups (NN, SN, SC), we observed statistically significant differences across a broad spectrum of parameters under examination— including morphology, motility, AO+, CMA3+ staining, and the extent of DNA-RNA oxidative damage. The p-values associated with these findings were all less than 0.001, indicating a high level of statistical significance in the variations noted between the groups for each measured parameter (Table 4).

Table 1: Comparison of semen parameters between cigarette smokers and non smokers.

Parameters	Non-smokers Group (G.1)	Cigarette Smoker Group (G.2)	P-Value
Sperm concentration (mi/mL)	59.64 ± 23.9	57.92 ± 21.6	p ≤ 0.487
Sperm Motility (%)	57.02± 11.15	60.7± 10.5	p ≤ 0.399
Immotile sperm (%)	44.59± 18.5	52.42± 24.3	p ≤ 0.296
Sperm morphology	7.34± 5.8	5.02± 4.8	p ≤ 0.152
Chromatin condensation (%) (CMA3)	14.68±15.64	25.28±14.86	p ≤ 0.024
DNA damage (Acridine Orange AO)	10.08± 14.2	16.5± 10.2	p ≤ 0.499

DNA-RNA Oxidative Damage (%)	40.74± 18.2	46.26± 19.3	p ≤ 0.464
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Table 2: Comparison of semen parameters between cannabis smokers and non smokers.

Parameters	Non-smokers Group (G.1)	Cannabis smoking (Group) G3.	P-Value
Sperm concentration (mi/mL)	59.64 ± 23.9	46.71 ± 18.1	p ≤ 0.159
Sperm Motility (%)	57.02± 11.15	46.21± 10.5	p ≤ 0.114
Immotile sperm (%)	44.59± 18.5	65.13± 21.8	p ≤ 0.006
Sperm morphology	7.34± 5.8	2.23± 2.1	p ≤ 0.001
Chromatin condensation (%) (CMA3)	14.68±15.64	34.83±18.39	p ≤ 0.001
DNA damage (Acridine Orange AO)	10.08± 14.2	28.5±15.8	p ≤ 0.481
DNA-RNA Oxidative Damage (%)	40.74± 18.2	88.42± 22.4	p ≤ 0.001

Table 3: Comparison of semen parameters between cigarette smokers and cannabis smokers.

Parameters	Smoker Group (G.2)	Cannabis Group (G.3)	P-Value
Sperm concentration (mi/mL)	57.92 ± 21.6	46.71 ± 18.1	p ≤ 0.168
Sperm Motility (%)	60.7± 10.5	46.21± 10.5	p ≤ 0.110
Immotile sperm (%)	52.42± 24.3	65.13± 21.8	p ≤ 0.791
Sperm morphology	5.02± 4.8	2.23± 2.1	p ≤ 0.001
Chromatin condensation (%) (CMA3)	25.28±14.86	34.83±18.39	p ≤ 0.025
DNA damage (Acridine Orange AO)	16.5± 10.2	28.5± 15.8	p ≤ 0.481
DNA-RNA Oxidative Damage (%)	46.26± 19.3	88.42± 22.4	p ≤ 0.001

Table 4:

One-Way ANOVA

One-Way ANOVA (Welch's)

	F	df1	df2	p
vol	1.88	2	71.09	0.161
count	1.67	2	73.35	0.195
morphology	15.44	2	63.61	< .001
Motility (PR+NP)	7.25	2	74.45	0.001
immotile	6.40	2	74.37	0.003
AO+	27.05	2	70.45	< .001
CMA3+	17.14	2	74.04	< .001
DANN-RNA Oxidative Damage	34.36	2	56.49	< .001

Group Descriptives

	Tobacco Smoking	N	Mean	SD	SE
vol	NN	37	2.73	1.21	0.20
	SN	40	3.31	1.43	0.23
	SC	38	2.92	0.83	0.14
count	NN	37	32.95	24.14	3.97
	SN	40	28.39	21.69	3.43
	SC	38	23.97	18.18	2.95
morphology	NN	37	7.46	5.92	0.97
	SN	40	5.03	4.82	0.76
	SC	38	2.26	2.29	0.37
Motility (PR+NP)	NN	37	48.68	18.98	3.12
	SN	40	40.95	24.30	3.84
	SC	38	30.82	21.42	3.47
immotile	NN	37	51.73	18.82	3.09
	SN	40	58.92	24.38	3.85
	SC	38	68.66	21.89	3.55
AO+	NN	37	10.08	14.21	2.34
	SN	40	6.35	10.15	1.61
	SC	38	28.53	15.80	2.56
CMA3+	NN	37	15.03	15.39	2.53
	SN	40	25.27	14.86	2.35
	SC	38	37.13	17.14	2.78
DANN-RNA Oxidative Damage	NN	37	1397.45	326.23	53.63
	SN	40	1362.65	114.05	18.03
	SC	38	1944.11	415.26	67.36

DISCUSSION

Tobacco smoking is one of the major factors contributing to male infertility ^[36], and surveys have indicated that approximately 120,000 young men (ages 30 to 50) in the United Kingdom are impotent because of this harmful habit. Studies on male smokers in infertile couples showed a lower ejaculate volume, despite them having higher testosterone levels ^[37].

Mounting evidence suggests that tobacco smoking substantially affects both the quality and quantity of sperm, thereby contributing to male infertility ^[38,39]. Conversely, some studies report no link between smoking and male infertility ^[40]. Nevertheless, the impact of smoking on sperm motility is still a subject of debate ^[41].

Earlier studies showed the adverse effect of cigarettes smoking on the progressive sperm motility and sperm morphology irrespective of the total number of cigarettes smoked daily ^[42,43,44,45].

Moreover, it has been reported that cigarette smoking was found to also affect Ca²⁺-ATPase activity of the spermatozoa as well ^[46]. In addition, different proteins (Aldoa, ATP5a1, Gpx4, Cs) expressed in sperms were significantly altered in smokers ^[47]. Based on previous studies, tobacco smoke has a wide range of harmful effects on male reproductive parameters and genome integrity ^[48,49].

In the present study, no significant differences in semen volume, sperm concentration or sperm count were found between the smoking and non-smoking groups (59.64 ± 23.9 Vs. 57.92 ± 21.6 mill/mL; p ≤ 0.48,7), sperm motility (57.02 ± 11.15 Vs. 60.7 ± 10.5%; p ≤ 0.399), the mean percentage of immotile sperm (44.59 ± 18.5 Vs. 52.42 ± 24.3%; p ≤ 0.296) and the mean percentage of morphologically normal spermatozoa (7.34 ± 5.8 Vs. 5.02 ± 4.8 %; p ≤ 0.152), the mean percentage of DNA damage (Acridine orange; 10.08 ± 14.2 vs. 16.5 ± 10.2%; p ≤ 0.499) and the mean percentage of DNA-RNA Oxidative Damage (40.74 ± 18.2 Vs. 46.26 ± 19.3; p ≤ 0.464).

Sperm chromatin condensation, however, was significantly lower in smokers (14.68 ± 15.64) compared to non-smokers (25.28 ± 14.86; p ≤ 0.024) as shown in (Table 1). In line with these findings, ^[50] reported that sperm viability markedly decreased, and DNA fragmentation rates significantly increased in smokers when compared to non-smokers (p < 0.05).

Apart from the sperm protamine content, the findings of the present study, showed a detectible deterioration of sperm parameters in the smoker group when compared to the non-smoker group. However, this observation did not reach the threshold of statistical significance.

Cigarette smoking has been found to detrimentally impact a range of conventional semen parameters, as well as sperm chromatin condensation and viability. Moreover, these negative effects correlate with both the quantity of cigarettes smoked daily and the overall duration of smoking. In a study conducted by, it was observed that the rate of histone abnormalities was significantly lower in non-smoking men with normal sperm counts, while the highest rates were found in heavy smokers with oligospermia within the Chinese population studied.

Human studies on the effects of tobacco consumption on semen parameters revealed that semen volume, total motility, percentage of morphologically normal spermatozoa, sperm vitality, and sperm membrane integrity were significantly decreased in smokers in comparison with non-smokers ^[51]. Moreover, several studies have reported that the spermatozoa of smokers have higher levels of DNA fragmentation in comparison with non-smoker ^[52].

Furthermore, oxidative stress and its markers such as ROS, malondialdehyde, and 8-hydroxyguanosine (8-OHdG), were significantly higher (p < 0.010) in smokers than in non-smokers and correlated significantly (p < 0.050) with P1:P2 ratios ^[53].

The present results are in consistent with other studies conducted by ^[54] who demonstrated that tobacco consumption may contribute to the progression of male infertility due to alterations in sperm characteristics. A comprehensive investigation compared 1165 male participants aged between 16 and 29 years was carried out in 2003-2004, showed that smoking exhibited detrimental effects on both sperm concentration and total sperm

counts; significantly lower sperm concentrations were recorded for smokers (median 60 versus 66 x 10⁶/ml, P=0.02) along with reduced total sperm counts (177 versus 226 x 10⁶, P<0.001) in comparison to non-smokers. Besides, these results are in agreement with others presented by who verified the detrimental effects of smoking on sperm parameters and concluded that a substantial reduction in sperm concentration and motility could be observed among smokers compared to non-smokers.

Reduced sperm counts, motility, viability, morphology, and inhibition of the acrosome reaction in humans can have drastic implications in the long term with regards to impairing male reproduction as well as negatively impacting the offspring ^[55,56]. Collectively, these findings underscore the significant negative consequences of tobacco smoking exerts on sperm cell function and fertility potential.

Numerous studies have provided insights into the multiple pathways through which tobacco smoking affects sperm cells. One salient mechanism is the direct toxicological impact of the constituents of cigarette smoke on testicular function. For instance, it has been discovered that nicotine impairs spermatogenesis by inducing oxidative stress, DNA damage, and apoptosis within germ cells, leading to reduced sperm count and motility ^[57,58]. Additionally, tobacco smoking is known to increase seminal reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels, which disrupts sperm functionality and results in decreased fertilization capacity.

Other possible mechanisms might be related to the negative impact of smoking on the 8 nAChR subunits found in human spermatozoa, resulting in smoking-related sperm damage.

On the other Hand, Cannabis, also known as marijuana, is derived from the dried leaves and flowers of the Cannabis sativa plant. People consume it for its psychoactive effects, such as relaxation and mild euphoria, or for its physiological benefits. Upon consumption, cannabis releases cannabinoids that interact with the body's endocannabinoid system (ECS), binding to cannabinoid receptors. In the United States, marijuana is the most used illicit drug and is gaining popularity as both a recreational substance and a medicinal aid, particularly among men of reproductive age.

However, our understanding of the long-term effects of exposure to marijuana is very poor and contradictory results have been reported. Also, cannabis smoking has garnered significant attention in recent years, particularly for its potential impact on various aspects of human health. Cannabis sativa and Cannabis indica are the most widespread and best-characterized species of cannabis; extracts of both plants contain phytocannabinoids of therapeutic interest, such as Δ⁹-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) and cannabidiol (CBD) ^[59,60].

Cannabis varies substantially in the level of its two major cannabinoids: delta-9-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) and cannabidiol (CBD). Levels of CBD can range from almost zero to up to 40%. THC is often associated with deleterious effects such as impaired cognition, anxiety, and psychotic-like symptoms, whereas CBD has been associated with antipsychotic and anxiolytic-like effects, and might even offer neuroprotection ^[61,62].

The FDA has approved two prescription cannabinoids: dronabinol, which is a synthetic version of Δ⁹-THC, and nabilone, a synthetic analogue of THC. Both medications are effective in treating chemotherapy-induced nausea and vomiting. Additionally, dronabinol and nabilone have been proven to be effective in managing pain and

distress. ^[63]. Whereas cannabidiol (CBD), which is another major component of marijuana, has been shown to decrease testosterone levels and impair spermatogenesis in animal models ^[64].

THC is known to bind to cannabinoid receptors in the testes, which can lead to decreased sperm motility, altered sperm morphology, and DNA. These effects may be due in part to the disruption of the endocannabinoid system, which plays a key role in regulating male reproductive function ^[65].

Although, the common adverse effects of cannabidiol (CBD) are well documented, and they include sleepiness, fever, decreased appetite, ataxia, vomiting, and abnormal behavior and sedation ^[66,67]. still, little is known about the long-term effect of (Cannabidiol) on hormone regulation, cognition/memory, fertility, and pregnancy ^[68].

Initially, there was lack of clarity regarding the presence of CB2 receptors in spermatozoa, but a study conducted by ^[69] confirmed the presence of the CB2 receptor in the postacrosomal region, midpiece, and tail of human spermatozoa. CB2 receptors were also found to be present on Sertoli cells.

Later studies revealed that daily administration of 12.5 mg/kg of cannabis for 30 days led to complete spermatogenesis arrest ^[70].

There is a growing body of evidence suggests that cannabis use may have adverse implications for male reproductive health, particularly regarding the viability and functionality of sperm. ^[71]documented a significant decrease in sperm concentration among cannabis users compared to non-users, while another study by ^[72]observed altered sperm morphology and DNA integrity from cannabis exposure ^[73].

It was also observed that the concentration and motility of sperm were negatively affected by frequent cannabis usage ^[74]. In an extensive literature review revealed a clear association between chronic cannabis use and reduced sperm count, sperm motility, and altered sperm morphology. The impact of cannabis on the motility of spermatozoa has been observed to decrease at both therapeutic and recreational levels of tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) ^[75].

Du Plessis investigated the underlying mechanisms and revealed that the primary psychoactive compound in cannabis, Δ -9-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC), could disrupt key signaling pathways involved in spermatogenesis and impair testosterone production. Consequently, this impairment may lead to reduced spermatogenic capacity and suboptimal sperm function. The accumulating research underscores the importance of understanding the potential risks associated with cannabis smoking on male fertility and highlights the need for further investigations to elucidate the full extent of its impact on sperm cells^[76].

It should be noted, however, that conflicting results exist in the literature regarding THC's influence on sperm quality. Notably, research conducted by ^[77]observed no significant variances in terms of sperm count, motility, or structure when comparing marijuana consumers with individuals who do not use the substance.

These discrepancies may be due to differences in study design, sample size, or participant characteristics ^[77].

In the present study, sperm concentration (59.64 ± 23.9 vs. 46.71 ± 18.1 mill /mL; $p \leq 0.15$) mean value of sperm motility (57.02 ± 11.15 vs. $46.21 \pm 10.5\%$; $p \leq 0.114$) and DNA fragmentation AO (10.08 ± 14.2 vs. $28.5 \pm 15.8\%$; $p \leq 0.481$) showed no significant difference between cannabis smokers and non- smokers. However, the mean percentage of immotile sperm (44.59 ± 18.5 vs. 65.13 ± 21.8 ; $p \leq 0.006$), sperm morphology (7.34 ± 5.8 vs. 2.23 ± 2.1 ; $p \leq 0.001$), sperm maturation (CMA3) (14.68 ± 15.64 vs. 34.83 ± 18.39 ; $p \leq 0.001$), DNA-RNA Oxidative Damage (40.74 ± 18.2 vs. 88.42 ± 22.4 ; $p \leq 0.001$) demonstrated a significant difference between non-smokers and cannabis smokers group.

These finding confirm previous study conducted on human by and other experimental study on animals ^[78] who demonstrated that sperm concentration decreased after exposure to cannabis. It also appears that sperm counts are inversely proportional to the amount of drug taken. Moreover, a large-scale prospective study by demonstrated a notable link between regular cannabis smoking and lower total sperm count in men when compared with individuals who had never smoked cannabis.

Pacey conducted a prospective trail included, 1,700 unmatched case reference study of men in the United Kingdom presenting at a total of 14 fertility clinics and found that men who had used cannabis in the 3 months prior to collection of a semen sample were more likely to have poor sperm morphology, defined as less than 4% morphologically normal spermatozoa (OR 1.94, 95% CI 1.05e-3.60).

Moreover, the findings of the present study are consistent with previous research that has demonstrated the negative effects of tetrahydrocannabinol (THC) on human sperm function and DNA integrity ^[79].

It is crucial to mention that cannabis smoke has been shown to have numerous toxicants and carcinogens including acrylonitrile (a potential carcinogen carbon monoxide cardiovascular toxin),⁶ and 1,3, -butadiene (a carcinogen) ^[80]. Very few published studies have examined cannabis smoke metabolites in humans.

Many Americans believe inhaling marijuana smoke is safer than inhaling tobacco smoke, a new study shows. Although the health effects of tobacco are well known, there is still some debate about the effects of cannabis use. In 2021, 44% of adults surveyed believed smoking marijuana every day is safer than smoking tobacco every day, compared to about 37% in 2017.

In one study, researchers examined cannabis smokers, cigarette smokers, and nonusers of either. Individuals who smoke cannabis have been found to exhibit significantly higher levels of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) compared to non-smokers. Their exposure is similar or even lower than that of individuals who smoke cigarettes. However, a statistical comparison between the effects of cannabis smoke and cigarette smoke has not been conducted.

Also, a significant increase in the mean percentage of immotile sperm (52.42 ± 24.3 vs $65.13 \pm 21.8\%$; $p \leq 0.006$), mean percentage of morphologically normal spermatozoa (5.02 ± 4.8 vs. $5.02 \pm 4.8\%$; $p \leq 0.001$), chromatin condensation (CMA₃) (25.28 ± 14.86 vs. $34.83 \pm 18.39\%$; $p \leq 0.001$) and DNA fragmentation (Acridine Orange; 16.5 ± 10.2 vs. $28.5 \pm 15.8\%$; $p \leq 0.012$) in cannabis smokers (G.3) in comparison to cigarette smoking group (G.2)

Also, DNA-RNA Oxidative damage rate was significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) in the Cannabis group (G3), compared with the tobacco smoker group (46.26 ± 19.3 Vs. $88.42 \pm 22.4\%$ respectively). The present data showed current or past Cannabis users had more damaged sperm, lower sperm counts and reduced the mean morphologically normal spermatozoa in comparison to cigarette smoking.

The current study revealed that the group of tobacco smokers experienced a significant decrease ($p \leq 0.024$) in the average percentage of sperm with properly condensed chromatin. Conversely, the cannabis-smoking group exhibited a considerable decline in sperm motility and the average percentage of morphologically normal spermatozoa, alongside reduced chromatin condensation (an indicator of sperm maturity). Additionally, this group showed a marked increase in the average percentage of immobile spermatozoa and the presence of DNA-RNA oxidative damage (Tables 1, 2, 3).

Previous study showed a similar decrease in sperm motility in an analysis of semen samples from 16 healthy, chronic marijuana users after 4 weeks of high dose marijuana. elucidated the mechanism of these findings by establishing a link between CB1 and sperm mitochondrial activity.

A follow-up study examined the effects of heaviness of cannabis smoking (ie, joints per day/month/year and never use) on polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) levels. Results indicated cannabis smokers who smoked two or more joints per day demonstrated higher levels of 2-hydroxynaphthalene, 2-hydroxyfluorene, and 1-hydroxypyrene than less frequent cannabis smokers. These studies indicate that individuals who smoke cannabis are subject to exposure to harmful toxic substances. As a result, those who concurrently use cannabis and tobacco could potentially face a greater risk of exposure to toxicants and carcinogens compared to those who only smoke cigarettes.

It is worth noting that the effects of marijuana on male reproductive function may be reversible with cessation of use. A study by found that men who stopped using marijuana for at least 74 days had significantly higher sperm concentration and motility compared to those who continued to use marijuana.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained in the present study showed that not only cigarette smoking but also cannabis smoking cause a deleterious effect on sperm concentration, motility, vitality, maturation, DNA fragmentation, and DNA-RNA Oxidative damage. However, more deterioration of spermatozoa quality was shown by comparing cannabis smokers to cigarette smokers and non –smokers. To further support to these findings, it is necessary to conduct additional research.

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